

Accepted Manuscript

Simultaneous synthesis of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes and amorphous carbon thin films on stainless steel

Pablo Romero, Raquel del Oro, Monica Campos, Jose M. Torralba, Roberto Guzman de Villoria

PII: S0008-6223(14)00982-8

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2014.10.020>

Reference: CARBON 9413

To appear in: *Carbon*

Received Date: 6 June 2014

Accepted Date: 12 October 2014

Please cite this article as: Romero, P., Oro, R.d., Campos, M., Torralba, J.M., Guzman de Villoria, R., Simultaneous synthesis of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes and amorphous carbon thin films on stainless steel, *Carbon* (2014), doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2014.10.020>

This is a PDF file of an unedited manuscript that has been accepted for publication. As a service to our customers we are providing this early version of the manuscript. The manuscript will undergo copyediting, typesetting, and review of the resulting proof before it is published in its final form. Please note that during the production process errors may be discovered which could affect the content, and all legal disclaimers that apply to the journal pertain.

Simultaneous synthesis of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes and amorphous carbon thin films on stainless steel

Pablo Romero¹, Raquel del Oro², Monica Campos³, Jose M. Torralba^{1,3}, Roberto Guzman de Villoria^{1,}*

[1] IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel 2, 28906, Getafe, Madrid, Spain

[2] Chalmers University of Technology, Rännvägen 2A, SE-41296 Gothenburg, Sweden

[3] Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Universidad Carlos III, Av. Universidad, 30, 28911, Leganés, Spain

* Corresponding author: roberto.guzman@imdea.org

KEYWORDS Carbon nanotubes, amorphous carbon thin film, chemical vapor deposition, stainless steel.

Abstract

Carbonaceous nanostructures such as carbon nanotubes, graphene and transparent carbon-based thin films are envisioned to be part of the next generation of electronic devices, mechanical structures, and energy-storage systems, etc. To synthesize these nanostructures on a large scale by chemical vapor deposition, large-area, flexible substrates are needed. Here, we studied the role of a metallic foil, stainless steel, as a self-catalytic substrate for carbon nanostructure synthesis. As a result, vertically aligned carbon nanotubes and amorphous carbon thin films were simultaneously obtained. We further showed that the evolution of the stainless steel foil during the different steps of the process played a critical role in carbon nanotubes and carbon thin film growth. A better understanding of how the growth of these carbon nanostructures is affected by stainless steel evolution under chemical vapor deposition conditions will enable the synthesis of hybrid carbon nanotubes/amorphous carbon thin-film nanostructures and pave the way to scale-up of their low-cost production.

1. Introduction

Because of the current interest in organized carbonaceous nanostructures such as vertically aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) or graphene-based films for mechanical reinforcement, electronic devices, and energy applications [1,2], among others, the production of large quantities of these nanostructures is needed. Chemical vapor deposition has shown the best results of all the synthesis techniques, in terms of production yield and versatility to produce large and organized carbonaceous structures. Flexible substrates which can be folded in a batch chemical vapor deposition reactor or used in a conveyor-belt reactor, as we previously demonstrated [3], will easily enable scaling up the synthesis of carbonaceous nanostructures such as graphene-based sheets of several square centimeters [4], or vertically aligned CNT forests [3].

Stainless steel is one of the best substrates for CNT synthesis [5–10]. Apart from its low cost and commercial availability, its chemical composition, rich in Fe and Ni, permits direct growth of CNTs without any pretreatment [8]. However, some pretreatments improve the length and yielding of CNTs in these metallic substrates, for example, a higher density of vertically aligned CNT forest was obtained by chemical etching of the substrate [6,7,9,11]. The etching treatment removes the Cr_2O_3 passive protection layer that is always present in stainless steels and which produces an increment of iron oxide on the steel surface [7]. Alternately, a simple oxidation–reduction pretreatment produces Fe catalytic nanoparticles on the stainless steel surface [6], as well as a surface oxide layer that plays an important role as a diffusion barrier between the Fe nanoparticle and the bulk substrate [12]. Mechanical treatments such as polishing [13] and argon ion bombardment [14] were also reported as effective stainless steel pretreatment methods.

One important effect of the high temperatures (500–1000°C) and hydrogen/hydrocarbon-rich atmosphere exposures in the different steps of the chemical vapor deposition process is the continuous evolution of the microstructure of the stainless steel, which may suffer several processes, such as formation of new phases [15], precipitation of carbon [16], or chromium migration [8], which may affect CNT growth.

In addition to CNT synthesis, both stainless steel [17] and pure iron foils [18] were recently used as catalytic substrates for the synthesis by chemical vapor deposition of polycrystalline graphene structures, which demonstrates the versatility and potential of Fe-based foils.

In the present work, we simultaneously synthesize vertically aligned carbon nanotubes and amorphous carbon (a-C) thin films directly on stainless steel foils obtained from the machine shop. A simple air oxidation treatment followed by chemical vapor deposition was used to synthesize the nanostructures. A detailed study of the extreme synthesis conditions in the stainless steel was performed, as substrate evolution is a key factor in the nanostructure

formation process [19,20]. The process demonstrated here is compatible with the novel generation of continuous chemical vapor deposition reactors [3,21] to produce the scalable and low-cost nanostructures needed for flexible electronic devices, energy, and composite materials, among other applications.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials and pretreatment process. A stainless steel foil type 304 (25- μm thick, Metall-Folien GmbH) was used as a catalytic substrate for vertically aligned CNTs synthesis through chemical vapor deposition. The composition of the foil was obtained by using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (Supplementary Information Table S1). The pristine stainless steel foil was cut into pieces approximately 20×10 mm. To clean the foil, it was dipped in ethanol and dried in air. The stainless steel foil was oxidized at 500°C for 30 min in a muffle furnace.

2.2. Vertically aligned CNTs and graphite thin-film synthesis. A custom-made chemical vapor deposition reactor was used. This system consisted of a furnace mounted on a wheeled mobile platform which allowed us to perform fast heating and cooling ramps by using the "*fast heat approach*" [22].

The oxidized stainless steel foil was placed in the middle of a quartz tube (22-mm diameter), positioned in a horizontal tube furnace (Nabetherm, R50/250/12). Once the continuous reactor was sealed, all the lines connected to the system were flushed for 10 min followed by 10 additional min of argon to displace trapped air from the system. The furnace was ramped to synthesis temperature with 100/400 sccm Ar/H₂ flowing, keeping the sample outside the heating zone. Several synthesis temperatures (from 716°C to 830°C) were analyzed. Once the required temperature was reached and stabilized, the furnace was rapidly moved (*ca.* 3 s) until the sample was located in the middle of the heating zone. The substrate reduction step took place for 10 min,

starting at room temperature. During this “fast heating”, the heating rate was about 500°C/min, as measured by a thermocouple placed outside the quartz reactor, below the sample. After the substrate reduction step, the reactant mixture of Ar/H₂/C₂H₄ (100/400/100 sccm) was introduced to allow the synthesis to proceed over 10 min. Once the CNTs and amorphous carbon thin film were grown, the furnace was moved back away from the sample to allow the sample to rapidly cool down to room temperature (exponential cooling down ramp from synthesis to room temperature is given in the Supplementary Information). During the cool-down, argon was flushed to purge any reactive gases of the system. Details of the parameters involved in the process can be found in the Supplementary Information.

2.3. Carbon nanostructures and stainless steel characterization. Vertically aligned CNTs and graphite thin films were analyzed by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, EVO MA15, Zeiss) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL JEM 3000F). CNTs were removed by cleaning a piece of the as-synthesized stainless steel foil in an ultrasonic bath with isopropanol. CNTs/isopropanol solution was analyzed afterwards. Amorphous carbon thin films were gently removed by acid etching these free-of-CNT foils (copper etchant, Sigma-Aldrich). For the high temperature synthesis conditions (780–830°C), the substrates were not easily dissolved in the acid, thus, tip sonication was applied to these samples to remove the amorphous carbon thin films. A drop of both solutions was carefully deposited on TEM Cu mesh (Ted Pella, inc). EDS analysis was also performed to obtain the composition of the different samples.

The as-synthesized samples were analyzed by using Raman spectrometry (Jasco, NRS-5100). The spectra were recorded directly on the stainless steel substrate after synthesis and from free-of-CNTs substrates, as well as from all the residues from CNTs removal and acid attack. A background spectrum of the oxidized SS foil was previously recorded. Three measurements for each sample were taken using a Nd:YAG green laser (534 nm, d=4000 μm). Spectra were

obtained for 2×20 s exposure over a range of $100\text{--}2750\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The effective laser power was 6 mW.

Surface chemical analyses were carried out by means of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) by using a PHI 5500 instrument (PERKIN ELMER, Eden Prairie, Minnesota, USA) with a monochromatic Al K (1486.6 eV) X-ray source. Chemical species present on the surface were identified by using survey scans over a wide range of binding energies ($1\text{--}1100\text{ eV}$). Determination of the chemical state of each element is possible by performing narrow scans with high energy resolution in the characteristic binding energy ranges of the elements of interest - in this case Fe, Cr, C, O, Si, Mn and Ni. Surface composition was estimated by curve fitting the characteristics peaks and converting their intensity into apparent atomic concentration, using standard relative sensitivity factors [20]. Depth profiles were obtained by sputtering the analyzed surface with Ar^+ ions to controlled depths and analyzing the etched surface. The etching rate was calibrated by using flat oxidized tantalum foil with the known oxide thickness. Etch depth is presented in tantalum oxide units that are close to the etching behavior of metallic oxides of interest [23].

Surface phases were also analyzed by using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, PANalytical model X'Pert PRO MRD) equipped with a Cu K α source ($\lambda = 0.154\text{ nm}$).

Finally, microstructural characterization of the substrate cross-section was carried out at the different steps of the process. For these characterizations, the samples were embedded in resin and mechanically polished to surface mirror finish, cleaned in an ultrasonic bath, and chemically etched (30 s in 3 HCl/1 HNO $_3$ vol.). A thin layer of gold (1 nm) was deposited by sputtering to analyze the sample by SEM (EVO MA15, Zeiss).

3. Results and Discussion

Vertically aligned CNTs forests were synthesized on oxidized stainless steel at a low temperature range (716–780°C) (Figure 1). Their length remained stable (about $4 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$) and they consisted of multiwalled CNTs of 20 ± 10 walls. Metal seeds were detected on the tip and along the length of the CNTs. Inside the CNTs only Fe was detected. An amorphous carbon film was detected on the stainless steel surface, beneath the CNTs. This a-C thin film, which was removed from the stainless steel by means of acid etching [24], is a graphene-like thin film formed by graphite nanocrystals [25,26], amorphous carbon, and Cr–Fe carbides nanoparticles.

For synthesis at a higher temperature range (780–830°C), a similar a-C film was obtained; in this case it was free of carbides or metallic nanoparticles but a few residual short CNTs (up to 1 μm) were observed. These CNTs were within the nanometer-length as opposed to the longer micrometer-length vertically aligned CNTs obtained at the low temperature range (below 780°C) (See Supporting Information for further characterization results).

The Raman spectra obtained for all the samples were similar in terms of peaks position and intensity, even for the substrates treated at higher temperature which did not produce vertically aligned CNTs forests. The characteristic peaks of defected graphite at about 1350 (D band), 1580 (G band), and 2690 cm^{-1} (2D band) are present in all samples (Supporting Information Figure S2).

The stainless steel foil was analyzed to enable us to understand its evolution after the oxidation pretreatment in air, and the two steps of the chemical vapor deposition process; the reduction step under Ar/H_2 , and the synthesis step under $\text{Ar}/\text{H}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ gas mixture. For more details see the Experimental section.

3.1. Surface composition analysis. Stainless steels present a thin native oxide layer at their surface that is mainly composed of Cr and Fe oxides. The composition depth profile of this as-received sample confirms the presence of Fe in the metallic state within this native oxide layer.

Specifically, 3 nm from the surface we found about 15 at.% of metallic Fe and an oxide ratio of about $\text{Fe}_{\text{cations}}/\text{Cr}_{\text{cations}} \bullet 0.35$ (Figure 2).

When oxidation treatment was performed, the oxide layer became thicker and metallic Fe signals decreased at the near surface (Figure 2). Compared to the preceding composition at 3 nm, we found about 5 at.% of metallic Fe, and a strong increment of $\text{Fe}_{\text{cations}}/\text{Cr}_{\text{cations}} \bullet 6$, so the oxide layer became thicker and was enriched with Fe cations upon oxidation treatment.

The reduction treatment at low temperature (716°C) affected the Fe cations more intensely, since chromium oxide is more stable under these conditions [27]. We found about 6 at.% of metallic Fe at 3 nm and again a low ratio of $\text{Fe}_{\text{cations}}/\text{Cr}_{\text{cations}} \bullet 0.3$. However, the reduction treatment at high temperature (830°C) led to a significant decrease of metallic Fe at 3 nm to 0.6 at.% and a ratio $\text{Fe}_{\text{cations}}/\text{Cr}_{\text{cations}} \bullet 0.12$, (Figure 2). At the temperatures used for the reduction treatments (716°C and 830°C), conditions can be reducing for iron oxides but strongly oxidizing for the more stable Cr oxides. When increasing the temperature to 830°C the enhanced kinetics of Cr oxidation lead to a decrease in the $\text{Fe}_{\text{cations}}/\text{Cr}_{\text{cations}}$ ratio and, since the surface is enriched in Cr oxides, metallic Fe detected in the surface is consequently lower.

Regarding the composition of the surface after the synthesis step at low temperature (Figure 3), we found 0.4 at.% of metallic Fe and a ratio of $\text{Fe}_{\text{cations}}/\text{Cr}_{\text{cations}} \bullet 0.16$ at 3 nm. In terms of carbon incorporation into the substrate after the next synthesis step, a small accumulation was detected at low temperature (26 at.% at 716°C). However, when the synthesis was conducted at higher temperatures (830°C), a significant increase of carbon up to 75 at.% was detected. As shown, carbon penetrated into the bulk, reaching values of about 26 at.% at a depth of 50 nm (Figure 3). It is important to mention that a carbon thin film was always present in the stainless steel surface after synthesis, so results presented in Figure 3 partially correspond to the composition of this

carbon film, which is filled of Cr–Fe carbides nanoparticles in the case of low temperature synthesis (see Figure 1).

3.2. Phase transitions on stainless steel. The variation of surface composition throughout the whole treatment suggests that phase transitions could take place in the stainless steel. The as-received stainless steel is composed of martensite while the as-oxidized stainless steel presents an austenitic microstructure. The fabrication process of the stainless steel foil produces a severe plastic deformation at room temperature that produced the martensitic microstructure [28]. Due to the thermal treatments, the austenitic microstructure is partially recovered after the oxidation step and to a greater degree after synthesis at 716°C. Reduction and synthesis at low temperature propagate the austenitic transformation as well as formation of metallic phases that likely contain Fe, Cr, and Ni. Higher synthesis temperatures led to formation of carbides ($\text{Cr}_{22,23}\text{Fe}_{0,77}\text{C}_6$) as shown in the corresponding spectra, whereas the austenitic transformation continued its course. Under an atmosphere rich in carbon species, the carbide formation is highly favored on the stainless steel at the synthesis temperatures [29]. For more details see the Supplementary Information Figure S3.

3.3. Cross-sectional microstructural analysis. Finally, an analysis of the substrate cross-section was conducted to identify the depth of the stainless steel evolution (Figure 4). The pristine stainless steel shows the typical deformed and acicular grain morphology of martensite, in agreement with the X-ray diffraction results. The black cavities correspond to the porosity created by Mn–Cr–O inclusions. We also observed that the martensitic microstructure remained after the oxidation step. Nevertheless, a recrystallization process took place at about 750°C and the grain size increased with the synthesis temperature. As expected from the X-ray diffraction results, a microstructure with chromium carbides spread throughout the cross-section is observed at about 810°C.

3.4. Stainless steel evolution and synthesis process. The stainless steel substrate evolves during the different steps of the carbon nanostructure formation, which will affect the synthesis process (Figure 5). The stainless steel oxidation treatment creates an Fe-richer and thicker oxide layer than the thin native oxide of the as-received steel, as demonstrated by XPS. After the next reduction step at low temperature (716°C), metallic Fe is recovered in the near surface of the substrate.

This oxidation//low temperature reduction treatment is believed to create finely dispersed catalytic active sites that consist of metallic Fe on the stainless steel surface [6]. Although metallic Fe seems not to be strictly needed for the synthesis of carbon nanotubes [30], the production of vertically aligned CNTs from oxidized/ low temperature reduced samples may be due to the high density of catalytic particles obtained [31]. On the other hand, the amount of metallic Fe in the surface is significantly lower for the samples reduced at high temperature (830°C). Probably, because of this low density of metallic Fe, vertically aligned CNTs forests, that were only achieved after oxidation/low temperature reduction treatment, are not observed for the high temperature reduced samples after the synthesis steps.

Because of the chemical vapor deposition conditions of high temperatures and carbon saturated environments, metal dusting takes place [13]. This process, which is well known in the steam reforming industry, is a form of corrosion that occurs at temperatures between 400–900°C under strongly carburizing atmospheres. Under these conditions, oversaturation of metal with dissolved C leads to its decomposition into dust that may be composed of carbon, oxides, carbides, and metal nanoparticles [32],[33]. These metal particles in the dust may act as catalysts for further carbon deposition [32], in the form of graphite and CNTs [20].

In this study, it seems that the deposition of carbon as a film on the substrate takes place *simultaneously* with the CNT growth, meanwhile surface dissociation caused by metal dusting

could create new catalytic nanoparticles within these carbon thin films. Although we found nanoparticles on the amorphous carbon thin film grown at low temperature by TEM (Figure 1c), it is not clear whether CNTs grow from them or from the metallic Fe created by the oxidation/reduction treatment. For the high temperature range (780–830°C) we detected i) a martensitic–austenitic transformation, ii) carbide formation, and iii) a growth in grain size of the stainless steel. All these findings are accompanied by the absence of vertically aligned CNTs and a significant enhancement of carbon incorporation in the near surface. These phenomena may be produced by an enhancement of carbon solubility in pure bulk iron from 700°C (*ca.* 0.1 at.% in ferrite) to 800°C (*ca.* 4 at.% atomic austenite) [15], the low amount of metallic Fe in the near surface after the high temperature reduction step and the recrystallization process, which creates grain boundaries as an effective carbon diffusion path [34].

4. Conclusions

In summary, we have simultaneously synthesized vertically aligned carbon nanotubes and amorphous carbon thin films directly on oxidized stainless steel substrates by chemical vapor deposition without adding an external catalyst.

A low temperature reduction treatment (716°C–780°C) of the oxidized stainless steel is a convenient pretreatment before chemical vapor deposition to synthesize vertically aligned carbon nanotubes in the oxidized stainless steel. Regardless of the temperature used for the chemical vapor deposition synthesis step, we always found an amorphous carbon thin film on the stainless steel surface that we could detach by means of acid etching. However, vertically aligned carbon nanotubes forests were only obtained in the low synthesis temperature range (716°C–780°C), meanwhile no vertically aligned CNTs forests were obtained from synthesis at above approximately 800°C.

Stainless steel evolved during all stages of the process and opens a discussion of the growth mechanism in this kind of substrates. In terms of composition, the oxidation step enriches the stainless steel surface with Fe_2O_3 that, in the next low temperature reduction step, partially turns back into metallic Fe. As a result a thicker Cr_2O_3 layer is also obtained that is believed to act as a carbon diffusion barrier. It is believed that after this low temperature reduction pretreatment, catalytic active sites on the stainless steel surface are produced [6], that may be responsible of the production of vertically aligned CNTs forests. In this regard, we found that this is achieved only after low temperature reduction (716-780°C), and nearly no metallic Fe is detected in the surface after high temperature reduction.

During the synthesis, nanoparticles are formed by metal dusting, a well-known process in the steam-reforming industry. At the same time, the bulk stainless steel suffers a martensitic to austenitic transition as well as a recrystallization and formation of Cr carbides. This recrystallization process defines grain boundaries that may act as carbon diffusion paths, and explains the significant increase of C content in the stainless steel after synthesis at 830°C.

Further studies regarding other metals present in stainless steel, like Mn, Ni or others, that may play an important role in the oxidation/reduction processes should be carried out.

The approach presented here is perfectly compatible with our previous work performed in a continuous chemical vapor deposition reactor [3] using flexible substrates; thus, based on this study, it is now possible to envision to scale up the production of these nanostructures by using low-cost substrates as low-cost stainless steel with no need of an external catalyst.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Program, NFRP project, PICIG12-GA-2012-33924. R.G.V. gratefully acknowledges the Spanish Ministry

of Science and Innovation for financial funding through the Ramon y Cajal Fellowship. The authors would like to thank J. C. Rubalcaba for early discussions and work on the chemical vapor deposition reactor, L. C. Herrera, for early work on the carbon nanotube synthesis, A. Gomez (CNME, UCM) for TEM imaging assistance, I. Carabias (CAI-XRD, UCM) for XRD assistance, and M. Angulo and J. L. Jiménez for machining and fabrication support.

Supporting Information Available: Stainless steel foil composition, synthesis process details, indicating flow, time, and temperature of each of the five steps, high resolution TEM images of multiwalled carbon nanotubes, Raman results of carbon nanostructures, X-Ray results spectra, moving reactor setup, cooling-down ramp, and characterization of the amorphous carbon thin films synthesized at low and high temperature.

Competing financial interests: The authors declare no competing financial interests

References

- [1] Volder MFLD, Tawfick SH, Baughman RH, Hart AJ. Carbon Nanotubes: Present and Future Commercial Applications. *Science* 2013;339:535–9.
- [2] Geim AK. Graphene: Status and Prospects. *Science* 2009;324:1530–4.
- [3] Guzmán de Villoria R, Hart AJ, Wardle BL. Continuous High-Yield Production of Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotubes on 2D and 3D Substrates. *ACS Nano* 2011;5:4850–7.
- [4] Bae S, Kim H, Lee Y, Xu X, Park J-S, Zheng Y, et al. Roll-to-roll production of 30-inch graphene films for transparent electrodes. *Nat Nanotechnol* 2010;5:574–8.
- [5] Sano N, Hori Y, Yamamoto S, Tamon H. A simple oxidation–reduction process for the activation of a stainless steel surface to synthesize multi-walled carbon nanotubes and its application to phenol degradation in water. *Carbon* 2012;50:115–22.
- [6] Vander Wal RL, Hall LJ. Carbon nanotube synthesis upon stainless steel meshes. *Carbon* 2003;41:659–72.
- [7] Masarapu C, Wei B. Direct Growth of Aligned Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes on Treated Stainless Steel Substrates. *Langmuir* 2007;23:9046–9.
- [8] Hordy N, Mendoza-Gonzalez N-Y, Coulombe S, Meunier J-L. The effect of carbon input on the morphology and attachment of carbon nanotubes grown directly from stainless steel. *Carbon* 2013;63:348–57.
- [9] Baddour CE, Fadlallah F, Nasuhoglu D, Mitra R, Vandsburger L, Meunier J-L. A simple thermal CVD method for carbon nanotube synthesis on stainless steel 304 without the addition of an external catalyst. *Carbon* 2009;47:313–8.
- [10] Camilli L, Scarselli M, Del Gobbo S, Castrucci P, Nanni F, Gautron E, et al. The synthesis and characterization of carbon nanotubes grown by chemical vapor deposition using a stainless steel catalyst. *Carbon* 2011;49:3307–15.
- [11] Martínez-Hansen V, Latorre N, Royo C, Romeo E, García-Bordejé E, Monzón A. Development of aligned carbon nanotubes layers over stainless steel mesh monoliths. *Catal Today* 2009;147, Supplement:S71–S75.
- [12] Bult JB, Sawyer WG, Ajayan PM, Schadler LS. Passivation oxide controlled selective carbon nanotube growth on metal substrates. *Nanotechnology* 2009;20:085302.
- [13] Hashempour M, Vincenzo A, Zhao F, Bestetti M. Direct growth of MWCNTs on 316 stainless steel by chemical vapor deposition: Effect of surface nano-features on CNT growth and structure. *Carbon* 2013;63:330–47.
- [14] Sabeti Nejad N, Larijani MM, Ghoranneviss M, Balashabadi P, Shokouhy A. Direct growth of carbon nanotubes on Ar ion bombarded AISI 304 stainless steel substrates. *Surf Coat Technol* 2009;203:2510–3.
- [15] Jourdain V, Bichara C. Current understanding of the growth of carbon nanotubes in catalytic chemical vapour deposition. *Carbon* 2013;58:2–39.
- [16] Röthlisberger A, Seita M, Reiser A, Shawat E, Spolenak R, Nessim GD. Investigating the mechanism of collective bidirectional growth of carbon nanofiber carpets on metallic substrates. *Carbon* 2013;63:498–507.
- [17] John R, Ashokreddy A, Vijayan C, Pradeep T. Single-and few-layer graphene growth on stainless steel substrates by direct thermal chemical vapor deposition. *Nanotechnology* 2011;22:165701.
- [18] Xue Y, Wu B, Guo Y, Huang L, Jiang L, Chen J, et al. Synthesis of large-area, few-layer graphene on iron foil by chemical vapor deposition. *Nano Res* 2011;4:1208–14.

- [19] Chun CM, Ramanarayanan TA. Metal Dusting Corrosion of Austenitic 304 Stainless Steel. *J Electrochem Soc* 2005;152:B169–B177.
- [20] Szakálos P. Mechanisms and driving forces of metal dusting. *Mater Corros* 2003;54:752–62.
- [21] Guzman de Villoria R, Figueredo SL, Hart AJ, Steiner SAI, Slocum AH, Wardle BL. High-yield growth of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes on a continuously moving substrate. *Nanotechnology* 2009;20:405611 (8pp).
- [22] Nessim GD, Seita M, O'Brien KP, Hart AJ, Bonaparte RK, Mitchell RR, et al. Low Temperature Synthesis of Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotubes with Electrical Contact to Metallic Substrates Enabled by Thermal Decomposition of the Carbon Feedstock. *Nano Lett* 2009;9:3398–405.
- [23] Olefjord I, Nyborg L. Surface Analysis of Gas Atomized Ferritic Steel Powder. *Powder Metall* 1985;28:237 – 243.
- [24] Mattevi C, Kim H, Chhowalla M. A review of chemical vapour deposition of graphene on copper. *J Mater Chem* 2011;21:3324.
- [25] Sun J, Lindvall N, Cole MT, Wang T, Booth TJ, Bøggild P, et al. Controllable chemical vapor deposition of large area uniform nanocrystalline graphene directly on silicon dioxide. *J Appl Phys* 2012;111.
- [26] Krivchenko VA, Pilevsky AA, Rakhimov AT, Seleznev BV, Suetin NV, Timofeyev MA, et al. Nanocrystalline graphite_Promising material for high current field emission cathode. *J Appl Phys* 2010;107.
- [27] Ellingham HJT. Transactions and communications. *J Soc Chem Ind* n.d.;63.
- [28] Mészáros I, Prohászka J. Magnetic investigation of the effect of α -martensite on the properties of austenitic stainless steel. *J Mater Process Technol* 2005;161:162–8.
- [29] Almanza E, Murr LE. A comparison of sensitization kinetics in 304 and 316 stainless steels. *J Mater Sci* 2000;35:3181–8.
- [30] Bonnet F, Ropital F, Berthier Y, Marcus P. Filamentous carbon formation caused by catalytic metal particles from iron oxide. *Mater Corros* 2003;54:870–80.
- [31] Bedewy M, Meshot ER, Guo H, Verploegen EA, Lu W, Hart AJ. Collective Mechanism for the Evolution and Self-Termination of Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotube Growth. *J Phys Chem C* 2009;113:20576–82.
- [32] Grabke HJ, Krajak R, Nava Paz JC. On the mechanism of catastrophic carburization:“metal dusting.” *Corros Sci* 1993;35:1141–50.
- [33] Young DJ, Zhang J, Geers C, Schütze M. Recent advances in understanding metal dusting: A review. *Mater Corros* 2011;62:7–28.
- [34] Szakalos P, Pettersson R, Hertzman S. An active corrosion mechanism for metal dusting on 304L stainless steel. *Corros Sci* 2002;44:2253–70.

Figures

Figure 1. Nanostructures synthesized. Vertically aligned CNTs forest obtained at low synthesis temperatures between (716–780°C) (a). Inset: metal seeds along the multiwalled CNT length. As the synthesis temperature increased, the length and alignment of the vertically aligned CNTs decreased, and led to a forest that was unobservable by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at 810°C synthesis temperature (b). Acid etching of the low temperature as-synthesized samples, marked by a black arrow on the inset (c), easily removed the amorphous carbon thin films marked by a white arrow. These amorphous carbon thin films presented Fe–Cr carbides detected by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (c). This same acid treatment did not remove the amorphous carbon thin film on the high-temperature samples, so tip sonication treatment was needed for their detachment (d). (See Supporting Information for Raman and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis).

Figure 2. Surface composition profile of stainless steel before the synthesis (Compositions calculated relative to Fe, Cr, C, O, Si, Mn and Ni). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of Cr and Fe surface composition profile of stainless steel on as-received, as-oxidized (30 min at 500°C in air), and as-reduced (a-h). Black, red, green, and blue are used on the left graph to denote the binding energies of 1-, 3-, 5-, and 10-nm depth, respectively. As-received stainless steel showed

metallic Fe 3 nm from its surface (a) at a concentration of about 15 at.% (e). Oxidation produced a thicker Fe-enriched oxide layer (cations signals) so metallic Fe decreased (b, f) to 5 at.% 3 nm from the surface. Reduction step at low temperature (10 min at 716 °C) (c, g) affected the Fe cations more intensely, so we found about 6 at.% of metallic Fe at 3 nm. Reduction step at high temperature (10 min at 830 °C) significantly decreased the amount of metallic Fe at 3 nm to 0.6 at.%.

Figure 3. Composition profile of Fe and Cr after synthesis for 10 min at 716°C (a), which indicates the predominance of Cr cations on the surface. A short accumulation of carbon occurred after synthesis at low temperature (716°C), however a significant increase of carbon incorporation into the substrate occurred at 830°C (b). It is important to mention that a carbon thin film was always present in the stainless steel surface after synthesis, so results these results partially correspond to the composition of this carbon film, which is filled of Cr–Fe carbides nanoparticles in the case of low temperature synthesis (see Figure 1). Compositions calculated relative to Fe, Cr, C, O, Si, Mn and Ni.

Figure 4. Microstructure evolution of a stainless steel. Stainless steel cross-section from as-received to as-synthesized at 810°C. Acicular grains corresponding to martensite microstructure were observed in as-received (a) and as-oxidized (b) samples. An increase of the grain size was detected after synthesis at 754°C and 780°C, and precipitation of carbides in the grain boundaries (d, e). Synthesis at 810°C led to big grains with a pronounced carbide formation across the whole cross-section (f).

Figure 5. Carbon nanostructures synthesis mechanism. The synthesis on stainless steel involves the simultaneous growth of CNTs and amorphous carbon thin film. Oxidation step creates a cationic Fe-rich thick oxide layer (a,b) and the reduction step partially reduces it back to metallic Fe (c). Vertically aligned CNTs and amorphous carbon thin film are simultaneously obtained at low synthesis temperatures (d).